

Lead City Journal of
Religions and
Intercultural
Communication
(ISSN 3043-4416)

(A Journal of the
Department of Religious
and Intercultural
Studies, Faculty of Arts,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria)

Editor in Chief
Samson IJAOLA, PhD

Editor
Adebayo Ola
AFOLARANMI, PhD

Associate Editor
Emmanuel O.
ADETUNJI, PhD

© 2025 Authors

Combining Digital Spiritual Formation with Oral Communication Methods to Enhance Discipleship with Rural Christian Youths among the Fali People of Adamawa, Nigeria

Linda Atuegbelo OGUNSHOLA

Lead City University, Ibadan

lindaogunshola@gmail.com, +2348053642166

Oluwaseun O. AFOLABI, PhD

Lead City University, Ibadan

oluwaseunafolabi@gmail.com

Abstract

In response to the diminishing level of discipleship and commitment to spiritual growth among the Fali Christian Youths (FCY), this study aimed to identify methods to boost spiritual commitment of FCY through digitalized orality-methods. Using the descriptive research design, this study investigated why digitalised oral teaching methods are relevant among the rural youths in Fali, Adamawa. The study also examined how digitalised orality methods can be used to enhance spiritual formation among the FCY of Mubi, Adamawa. The theoretical framework adopted was the Positive Youth Development theory. The findings revealed that a larger percentage (67%) of the respondents who are all youths have had secondary school level education, while about a quarter are barely literate, establishing the fact that the society is at the stage of secondary orality where textuality in combination with orality-methods prepared Biblical inputs, made accessible to them through digital technological means, will boost their spiritual formation. Approaches to employ with the digital outlets available to the FCY were enumerated as viable avenues for connecting with them as a discipleship community. The study concludes that digital intervention is the way out for improving spiritual formation and recommends that the churches facilitate and fund it.

Keywords: Digital Intervention, Spiritual Formation, Discipleship, Orality, Textuality, Fali People

Introduction

The nature of the world today as it concerns reading, literacy, and orality shows constantly changing dynamics and statistics. Africa has had a good share of changing statistics as regards literacy rates, as much efforts have continued to

be poured into making Africa literate. In Nigeria as at 2024, the literacy rate is sixty-nine percent (69%), making illiteracy rate thirty-one percent (31%) (Development Aid, 2024). This rate is as unstable as the security issues in the northeast, northwest, north central which keep rendering whole communities into Internally Displaced People's (IDP) camps, and the number of out-of-school children keep increasing (Development Aid, 2024). However, the percentage of those who can marginally read who continue to read as a regular practice is very low. Among the educated who are good at reading, the reading culture has been experiencing a downward trend, due largely to technological advancement that favour digital entertainment, weak educational systems that focus on memorization for exam success (The Cable, 2025). The decline in reading culture has rendered many literate people into oral learners.

Oral means of communication are either face to face as in the pre-digital age, or can be done from a distance through various technological mediums. Technology has therefore made it possible to reap the benefits of direct oral communication between persons who are far apart. Further benefits of digitalisation include the fact that platforms can be created which store these communications for repeated hearing by the listeners, making it possible for distance learning among oral learners to be possible (Emigh, 2024).

Fali people of Mubi North Local Government Area (LGA) in Adamawa State, Nigeria, are indigenous to the Mandara highlands that span the border between northeast of Nigeria and the northwest of Cameroun. Accessing their communities from the seat of the LGA – Mubi -involves climbing mountainous terrains through dust roads (Ogunshola, 2015). The Fali tribe comprises seven subtribes whose dialects are different enough to warrant at least two separate Bible translation efforts (Luke Initiative for Scripture Translation [LIST], 2022). The major settlements of the Fali, which are also subtribes are Vimtim, Muchalla, Bahuli, Pagra, Mijulu, Julvu, and Kirya. Each of the settlements has a Chief over the several villages under their subtribe. The Chiefs report to either of the two district heads who report to the Emir of Mubi administratively under Local Government. Some of the Fali communities are in the plains before the mountain ranges and their major markets are situated in the plains.

The Fali people living on the mountains and the plains have had the privilege of Christian mission work for more than four decades, have primary and secondary schools available to those who wish to attend. Even though most of the youths can read and write, the need for additional avenues to disciple the Fali is apparent due to the observed reduction in spiritual life and discipleship among them, resulting in apathy towards the Great Commission. Fali youths have in recent years been very enterprising farmers and traders across the

border with Cameroun. They possess cell phones and have access to some internet facilities in certain locations in their villages so that they do maintain communications through the internet with the outside world.

Biblical Foundations for Spiritual Formation and Discipleship

The Great Commission is not only a call to proclaim the ‘good news’ but a holistic discipleship that encompasses teaching, community formation, and long-term spiritual growth (Matthew 28:18-20; Acts 1:8). It is an integral mission for nurturing deep, sustained engagement with individuals and cultures in their journey toward following Christ (Chukwunonso, Chika, Kanu, Nganwuchu, and Chiazon, 2024). In the modern age, the instructions laid out by Christ remain relevant and even more urgent than ever, due to the increasing globalisation and interconnectedness of the world, as well as the population explosion of the world. There has never been a time in history when the multitudes needing the Gospel message and spiritual growth have been this many. This implies that the making of disciples in this age goes beyond geographical boundaries, cultures and diverse perspectives. This is why knowledge of the expectations of the Great Commission and the ways the early apostles carried it out, is necessary so as to adapt to changing cultures (Hughes, 2004).

Spiritual formation often refers to the process and practices that a believer in Christ needs to go through in order to become Christ-like. It is usually a life-long process of continuous spiritual growth in various spiritual disciplines, both personal (such as prayer, fasting, Bible Study and meditation, and learning God’s will), as well as with other believers (as corporate worship, accountability and mentoring relationships, and service to others). The natural outcome of sound spiritual formation in any Christian is firstly becoming Christ-like in character (discipleship), followed by the desire to spread God’s Kingdom beyond himself and to make Christ known to others in evangelism and missions, which could take different forms (French, 2023)

Orality, Literacy and Textuality

Orality has to do with anything that humans speak. Literacy has to do with anything that humans write. Converting sound to script is textuality. A society that has never had contact with writing is termed as being in the stage of primary orality, while a society that has been influenced by prints (texts) yet still has a strong oral component and is exposed to technology, is termed as being in the stage of secondary orality (Walter Ong, 1982). Orality is at the core of every society, even highly literate ones. Orality is present in every manuscript page

even if it is written (Reichl, 2023). Many scholars have brought forth different views about the relationship between orality, literacy and textuality. Even though orality precedes all forms of communication, orality, literacy and consequently digitalization are all forms of communication that can be used simultaneously. When combined, they give deeper and better clarity than what a single one would provide (Emigh, 2024).

Case for Orality Methods

Orality and textuality complement one another hermeneutically in communication (Hombana, 2025). Oral learners are those who learn best and can be impacted best when oral forms of communication are used. However, for oral learners, presentations prepared in literate-style are difficult to understand when presented audibly. This is because audibility is not equal to orality. Literate styled presentations confuse oral learners. Oral methods hold its own peculiar views.

Story telling is universally understood. More people prefer stories and symbols – concrete rather than philosophical concepts. Minds and hearts are touched by stories and emotions are involved.

Oral methods use concrete ways of processing information by being sequential in expressing events and making use of relational contexts. Theoretical concepts are abstract to oral learners. They should be complemented or replaced by well narrated stories, pictorial objects/characters. The stories connect the Bible script to Christ and then to the situations in the people’s lives and should be participatory in group settings. Literate methods are usually prepared in linear forms and outlines. They are abstract, random and individualistic. Textual supplements used together with stories should be a blend of oral and literate forms of communication (ION& LCWE. 2004).

Hybridisation of Orality, Textuality and Digitalisation for Spiritual Formation among Rural Youths

Writing and printing transformed thought patterns of humans and brought revolutions to the dissemination of information including exchange of ideas among other developments. Digitalisation has given wings to both the oral message and the written word in recent years. For effective dissemination of Biblical truth towards enhancing spiritual formation and discipleship, a blend of orality, textuality and digitalization gives room for each to complement the other (Finnegan, 1988, p7).

Digital evangelisation and discipleship has become a necessity as billions of humans can be accessed via the internet who ordinarily would have been

unreachable. Opportunities abound in this field, though there are a few threats to be cautious about such as the addictive nature of social media and the large amount of unwholesome inputs (Banaszak, 2022).

In another study, a scholar looked into the digital world as an opportunity to engage people with whom contact is restricted. Drawing from the experience of the COVID-19 social distancing experience, he posits that digital media is authentic, practical and has the potential to influence people spiritually. It aids access to the unreached even though the limitation of lack of power and poor internet in many rural areas creates handicap to the effectiveness of online or digital ministry. For the purpose of world evangelisation, social media is a sure way to disseminate the good news using different aspects of the media (Afolaranmi, 2020).

The proliferation of various capacities of solar power devices has greatly removed the handicap of power for digital ministry in rural areas. Digitalisation offers transformative opportunities for spiritual formation which have proven to increase youths' levels of spirituality (Chua et al,2024).

Use of technology has become rampant among adolescents and youths who generally comprise over half of the populations of most developing countries, especially in Africa. Nigeria has a youth population (18 -35 years) of over forty-two percent (42%) (NPC, 2022). In a study in Indonesia, it was discovered that the generational shift among the young majority has resulted in a struggle by churches to effectively engage these youths through the traditional methods due to the digital impact on their lives. Exploring digital means to engage the youths is a promising strategy for the church (Sampe, Sandaran, and Sule, 2025). The causes of youth disenchantment with traditional modes of worship include rigid worship structures which have less interactions and visual contents (Jeary Yip & Chang-Yau, 2016). Paying attention to the ways youths are impacted provides the church with ideas on effective methods to address issues of spiritual formation among them. Digitalisation offers transformative opportunities for spiritual formation among rural youths with low levels of education when the materials are orally prepared and delivered, and not just literate texts made audible (Chua, Soo And Raza, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

Positive Youth Development Theory (PYD)

The Positive Youth Development theory takes the position that youths in themselves are not a problem to be solved, rather they are potentials to be developed. Many scholars have had inputs into the PYD theory. However, P. L. Benson and R. M. Lerner are recognised as key scholars and practitioners of the

PYD theory and practice. They have provided frameworks on how to enhance youths' potentials in all spheres of life including the spiritual, by focusing on their strengths, potential and active participation in shaping their communities (Lerner et al, 2016; Benson and Pittman, 2001). One major position in the practice of PYD theory and practice is the readiness to abandon the status quo for innovations that can promote progress in the lives of young persons. The process of PYD is necessarily in the context of relationships that influence them, laying emphasis on correct mentoring relationships for the youths positively.

Statement of the Problem

The focus of this paper and the problem it seeks to address is the possibility of enhancing spiritual formation and discipleship among the Fali youth population through digitally disseminated materials tailored for secondary oral learners, for teaching and training. The case is for digital spiritual formation and discipleship as means for revamping ailing spiritual engagement and providing minimal missions training to the Fali Christian youths (FCY).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the utilisation of a hybrid of orality based digital spiritual formation programme with rural Christian youths among Fali people of Mubi, Adamawa, Nigeria. The objectives are:

- i) to ascertain why digitalized oral teaching methods will be relevant among Fali rural youths;
- ii) to ascertain the approaches that combine orality methods with digital discipleship for consistent spiritual growth among the Fali Christian Youths (FCY).

Methodology

This study set out to explore approaches of effecting spiritual formation through combining oral methodologies with digital technology among rural youths in Fali, Adamawa, Nigeria. It adopted the descriptive survey research design. The instruments used were questionnaire and interview guide. The population of the study was Mubi North LGA 233,600 (NPC, 2022). One hundred and fifty (150) copies of a questionnaire were administered to a total of one hundred and fifty (150) youth respondents, (fifteen in each of the ten selected congregations) with the following specifications: ages between eighteen and thirty-five; have been members of the church congregations purposively selected for upward of eight years on the average; must be Fali indigenes resident in the Fali communities selected. Interviews were conducted

for 50 respondents, comprising three youths who had been involved in missionary outreaches, a pastor and an elderly informant from each of the ten congregations purposively selected for the survey. There was a total of five interview respondents in each of the ten selected congregations, making a grand total of fifty interview respondents.

The communities and congregations selected are Christ’s Disciples’ Missionary Foundation (CDMF) Madivi, Julvu, Grace Evangel Mission (GEM) Madivi, Julvu, CDMF Lila, Julvu, CDMF Gilmari, Julvu, GEM Muhura, Julvu, United Gospel Faith Tabernacle (UGFTC) Mireyin, Mijulu, UGFTC, Lila, Julvu, CDMF Gubi, Mijulu, CDMF Muchalla 1, CDMF Muchalla 2.

The selected congregations are all led by indigenous Fali pastors today.

The data collected for the study were analysed using simple percentages, descriptive analysis, content and thematic analysis.

Findings

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of the Questionnaire Respondents

Construct	Distribution	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	100ss	67%
	Female	50	33%
Age	18-23 years	37	25%
	24-29 years	43	29%
	30-35 years	70	46%
Tribe	Fali	150	100%
Local government	Mubi	150	100%
Community	GILMARI JULVU	15	10%
	GUBI MIJULU	16	11%
	LILA JULVU	29	19%
	MADIVI	30	20%
	MIR MIJULU	15	10%
	MUCHALLA	30	20%
	MUHURA JULVU	15	10%
Church/Mission	CDMF	77	52%
	GEM	44	29%
	UGFTC	29	19%
Duration of membership	0-5 years	2	1%
	6-10 years	63	42%
	11 years and above	85	57%
Educational level	Primary Education	33	22%

Vocation	Secondary education	100	67%
	OND/NCE	13	9%
	HND/BA/BSC	3	2%
	Postgraduate education	1	1%
	Technical Skills (Artisan)	8	5%
	Agriculture	141	94%
	Others	1	1%

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 1 shows the questionnaire respondents were youths within the age bracket of eighteen to thirty-five years, were all Fali people resident within the rural communities surveyed. They all had been within the church setting for the between eight and ten years on the average, meaning that ideally, they should have grown spiritually and be disciplined to a great extent within those years.

Educational Level of the Respondents

Table 1. shows that sixty-seven percent (67%) of the respondents have secondary education as their highest educational level, while 22% have either primary school leaving certificates or did not pass through formal education. Only 12% have higher educational qualification. This implies that the majority of Fali Christian youth targeted for digital spiritual formation inputs in Mubi, Adamawa State, do not hold higher degrees in formal education; rather, they are engaged in farming and other vocations. This is further established in the vocational rows of Table 1, where 94% of the respondents are involved in agriculture; the 5% who are artisans also indicated that they are farmers, showing that 99% of the respondents are engaged in farming as their major or minor vocation, regardless of their educational qualifications. These data make it clear that the Fali communities surveyed are oral societies and even those who can read do not by virtue of their farming occupation spend much time reading. Because of the minimal level of literacy among them, they are secondary oral communities where a combination of oral teachings via storytelling and the use of written texts are the basics that guide the preparation and delivery of the digitally disseminated teachings. The data on the demography of the FCY show that oral methods will be appropriate for digital spiritual formation programme among them.

Qualitative Responses

Further analysis of the interview participants' responses reveals several interrelated themes that explain the spiritual tempo of the FCY and further buttress the relevance of digital intervention in their spiritual formation and missions training inputs.

- 1. *Spiritual Formation and Discipleship:*** A dominant theme highlights the need for renewal of spiritual commitment and discipleship as an indication of the need for extra inputs. Responses such as “Renewal of basic discipleship teachings and need for more consecration” and “Spiritual life revival will lead to more consecration to God and more commitment to serve God as cross-cultural missionaries” highlight the belief that personal holiness, devotion, and spiritual readiness are foundational to fruitful Christian life and mission work. Other suggestions, including “Churches to pray more and use their funds to help the youths” and “Return to Bible teachings and examples in the churches,” reinforce the view that structured spiritual mentorship and prayer support can catalyse youth commitment to spiritual disciplines and obedience to Biblical teachings. This is a pointer to the need for digital intervention for spiritual upliftment.
- 2. *Mission Education and Theological Training:*** A significant number of responses advocate for formal education and training in mission work, including theological instruction. Statements such as “More mission/theological education,” “Send youths for Missions and Theological Schools,” and “Enlarge and upgrade the Mission Training programmes to offer higher competencies” indicate that equipping youths with doctrinal knowledge, missional theory, and practical competencies is viewed as critical to enhancing confidence and effectiveness in discipleship and disciple-making. The emphasis on integrating mission education into broader educational pathways underscores the importance of orality cum textually blended instructional materials, digitally relayed for the Fali Christian Youths' spiritual formation.
- 3. *Institutional and Structural Support:*** The data also emphasise the role of churches and mission agency in fostering youth participation in digital group platforms formation and implementation of the programme especially for training purposes. Responses such as “Planted churches to support and encourage the youths who show interest in the Great Commission”, “Help youths financially from the churches,” and “Go out to mission fields with them as a way of mentoring them” suggest that both material and mentorship support are critical. Additionally, allowing

youths to take leadership roles (“Give room for youths to lead and show their potentials”) could build confidence and promote ownership of mission initiatives. These underscore the fact that digital intervention is needed also in providing mentorship for the youths to complement what the pastors are able to offer, and that these digital interventions are possible with the cooperation of the church leadership.

- 4. *Utilisation of Modern Platforms and Innovative Training:*** Participants noted the potential for technology-mediated training, particularly through social media and online resources, to expand access to mission education: “Training opportunities on social media should be utilised by youths.” This highlights a contemporary approach to enhancing engagement by leveraging digital platforms to provide flexible and scalable learning experiences.

In all, the responses reveal optimistic prospects for increasing FCY’s levels of discipleship, contingent on addressing spiritual, educational, vocational, and institutional needs. The recurring emphasis on holistic preparation—combining spiritual revival, theological training, skills acquisition, and mentorship—suggests that future programs must adopt integrated strategies rather than focusing on a single intervention. The integrated strategies would include paying attention to how the materials are prepared to achieve best understanding for the recipients.

Discussion of Findings

The Relevance of Digitalised Oral Teaching Methods as Spiritual Formation Intervention

As a result of the findings on the low educational levels of most Fali Christian Youths, where only twelve percent of them have attained education beyond the secondary school and about a quarter are barely literate, it is clear that they are secondary oral learners. Secondary oral learners are better impacted through orality-based methods. Furthermore, the finding that over ninety percent of them are occupationally farmers despite their level of schooling sheds light on the fact that they have little time for reading and that digital oral messages are best suited to boost their levels of spiritual formation. The exposure of these ones to the social media and their suggestions that missions and other trainings be brought to the youths through digital and social media confirms their readiness for digital intervention for spiritual formation, discipleship and missions training.

The Approaches to Combine Orality Methods with Digital Discipleship for Consistent Spiritual Growth among the Fali Christian Youths

Participants suggest leveraging technology and social media as contemporary avenues for training, communication, and awareness. Responses such as “Use of technology, social media should be incorporated” and “Train them in such a way that they can boldly enter new cultures with vocations and skills that will open the doors for the Gospel” underscore the importance of modern methods for equipping youths, particularly in cross-cultural contexts where access to traditional training may be limited. The Positive Youth development theory comes in here as a guide: that youths should be adequately impacted in the right direction with correct instructions and mentoring, in order to enhance their hidden potentials towards positive and productive participation in their own lives, family and community (Benson, 2001). Furthermore, the strategies identified in this study reflect a holistic and multi-layered approach to enhancing youth spiritual growth and engagement in the Great Commission.

Approaches to Employ in the Preparation of Digital Spiritual Formation Materials

Story telling as a method in oral communication needs to be strategically done in order to help the hearers visualise, understand, and be able to re-tell the story. Bible stories should be related sequentially, visualised as much as possible (by gestures and other visuals) in order to carry the learners along. With the use of well thought out facilitating questions the lessons embedded can be related and applied to the life situations. Group discussions give room for participation by everyone. Bible story telling is incomplete without a practice or assignment for the participants to tell the same story to someone else (Discipling for Development Bible Telling Manual, 2021).

Apart from stories, Bible text memorisation should be part of the weekly package to be digitally disseminated. On the site group meetings on weekly basis will create room for active discussions and feedback from individuals on lessons imbibed.

A blended discipleship package with these components which can be downloaded and listened to many times:

- Daily short audio devotionals prepared from Bible stories with two to three lines of text which would be appropriate for oral learners (non- literates) and persons with low education, disseminated via Facebook Messenger App and other similar media.

- Mentoring groups of eight to twelve youths who meet weekly on-site with online inputs. This could be through Facebook Messenger and WhatsApp having trained mentors to anchor the sessions in different communities.
- Digital discipleship and mentoring training for youth leaders who will thus be equipped to provide pastoral care and grooming in spiritual formation. These will serve as mentors for the small groups.
- Monthly digital renewal orality-based teaching sessions as summaries of the daily and weekly digital inputs.
- It should be noted that these digital inputs should enable relationships (mentoring, small groups), not replace them.

Conclusion

This study observed that the dwindling spiritual commitment due to low levels of spiritual formation and discipleship among Fali Christian Youths can be remedied through digital intervention. It discovered that orality based digital inputs are relevant methods to use for the FCY because they are secondary oral learners though with minimal levels of literacy and education; they have access to internet facilities and are exposed to social media; they actually recommended spiritual inputs and missions training to be made available to them through social media and other online avenues. The study also determined that a blend of orality-methods based teachings with minimal textual inputs should be disseminated digitally to them and that the church leadership should facilitate and supervise group meetings on-site. The youths being targeted for this intervention are not a problem, rather they are assets for the progress of the churches and communities in Fali. Digitalisation is appropriate for the youths' positive development

In conclusion, this study shows that combining digital spiritual formation with orality methods will enhance discipleship among youths who dwell in rural and difficult-to access areas as mentors can be trained online to monitor such processes.

Recommendations

In response to the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. In order to address the need for spiritual renewal and the return to discipleship foundation among Fali Christian youths, leaders of mission agencies and churches involved in cross-cultural mission work among them should work hand in hand to set up teams to address digital intervention to the issue.

2. The teams set up should develop orality based spiritual formation curriculum using story telling methods for teaching Bible truths through social media platforms.
3. The local Pastors and youth leaders should be trained as mentors to facilitate group meetings as they access the online inputs.
4. Church funds should be released to fund the needs that will arise as a result of the use of social media and the on-site aspects of the digital interventions.

References

- Afolaranmi, O. A. (2020). "Towards the Possibility of Internet Ministry as an Alternative Pastoral Ministry in Nigeria during the COVID-19 Pandemic," *International Journal of Information Technology and Language Studies (IJITLS)*, Vol. 4, Issue 2, Pp 12-26
- Banaszak, A. (2022). "Evangelization through Social Media – opportunities and threats to the religious life of an individual and community", *Journal: KOSCIOL: Prawo* 11, no. 2, 45-62.
- Benson, P. L., & Pittman, K. (2001). Moving the youth development message: Turning a vague idea into a moral imperative. In P. L. Benson & K. J. Pittman (Eds.), *Trends in youth development: Visions, realities, and challenges* (pp. vii–xii). Norwell, MA: Kluwer Academic Publishers
- Benson, P. L. (1997). *All Kids are our kids: What communities must do to raise caring and responsible children and adolescents*, San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Carson, D. A. (1984). "Matthew," in *The Expositor's Bible Commentary: Matthew, Mark, Luke*, ed. Frank E. Gaebelain, vol. 8 (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan Publishing House, 595.
- Chua, Catherine Siew Kheng, Soo, Johannah Li Mei, and Raza Kashif. (2024). "Work-Integrated (Adult) Learning: Un-Stigmatizing Blue-Collar Adult Learners in Singapore by Embracing Visibility," *Journal of Adult and Continuing Education* 30, no. 1 (May 2024): 112–30, <https://doi.org/10.117/14779714241228847>.
- Egwu, F. E. (2024). Development Aid. <https://www.developmentaid.org/news-stream/post/187820/nigeri-literacy-crisis>
- Emigh, Rebecca, Jean, "Wither Digitality? The Relationship Between Orality, Literacy and Digitality, Past and Present: From Spoken Traditions to Digital Media", *Annu. Rev. Sociol.* 2024. 50:715–36. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-soc-033022035644>
- Finnegan R. 1988. *Literacy and Orality: Studies in the Technology of Communication*. Oxford, UK: Blackwell 732; IP: 102.89.68.251
- Fleming BJ. 2016. The materiality of South Asian manuscripts from the University of Pennsylvania MS Coll. 390 and the R^{amam}_al^a library in Bangladesh. *Manuscr. Stud.* 1(1):28–51
- The Cable, 2025, <https://www.thecable.ng/the-alarming-decline-of-the-reading-culture>

- French, Katie (2023). "What is Spiritual Formation and Why Does It Matter?". <https://www.logo.com/grow/what-is-spiritual-formation-and-why-does-it-matter/>
- Global Ministries Christian Church (Disciples of Christ) and the United Church of Christ. https://www.globalministries.org/resource/college_of_mission_missionary
- Holy Bible, Matthew 28: 18-20; Mark 16:15-16; 2 Timothy 2:2
- Hombana, M., "Hearing the Text, Seeing the Text: Mazamisa on Orality and textuality" in die Skriflig 59(1),93185. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ids.v59i1.3185>
- Hughes, D. (2004) "Holistic Mission." Pattaya, Thailand: Lausanne Movement. <https://lausanne.org/occasional-paper/holistic-mission-lop-33>
- Jeaney Yip and Chang-Yau Hoon (2016). "To Build a Generation of Stars': Megachurch Identity, Religion and Modernity in Indonesia," South East Asia Research 24, no. 4 (December 1, 2016): 477–91, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0967828X16674132>
- Lerner, R. M., Lerner, J. V., Urban, J. B., & Zaff, J., (2016). Evaluating programs aimed at promoting positive youth development: A relational development systems-based view. Applied Developmental Science, 20(3), 175-187.
- Luke Initiative for Scripture Translation, (LIST) Nigeria (2022). *The Book of Luke in Bogghom*. <https://listng.net/what-we-do/scripture-engagement/book-of-luke-in-bogghom>
- LIST Nigeria (2022). *The Book of Luke in Tiyaa*. <https://listng.net/what-we-do/scripture-engagement/book-of-sluka-in-tiyaa>
- [The Navigators \(2021\). Discipling for Development, Bible Telling Manual.](#)
- Ong WJ.(1982). Orality and Literacy: The Technologizing of the Word. London: Methuen
- Reichl, Karl (2023). "Orality, Vocality, and Textuality". <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/36567800>
- Rev. N, Chukwunonso Joseph Offordile, Rex Chika, Ven Dr. Kanu, and Nganwuchu Geoffrey Chiaz0 (2025). "The Mission Statement of Jesus in Mathew 28:19 and Its Relevance to the Contemporary Christians Society." *Multidisciplinary Journal of Law, Education and Humanities* 1, no. 1 (2024).
- Sampe, Naomi, Sanderan Rannu, Sule Berna (2025). "Digital Discipleship in the Age of Connectivity: Insights for Transforming Ecclesiastical Practices in Indonesia". *Journal of Youth and Theology*, August 2025, pp 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1163/24055093-BJA10090>